

CORRECTION

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Correction to: Jasmonate-mediated defence responses, unlike salicylate-mediated responses, are involved in the recovery of grapevine from *bois noir* disease

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Correction

Following publication of the original article [1], it came to the attention of the authors that they had omitted to acknowledge the University of Parma. The Acknowledgement section should read as follows: “The authors kindly acknowledge the University of Parma (Department of Chemistry, Life Sciences and Environmental Sustainability; formerly Department of Life Sciences/Evolutionary and Functional Biology) for the transfer of funds obtained from the Ager project: GIALLUMI DELLA VITE: TECNOLOGIE INNOVATIVE PER LA DIAGNOSI E LO STUDIO DELLE INTERAZIONI PIANTA/PATOGENO, BANDO AGER VITICOLTURA DA VINO”.

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